

Implementation of a Smart Manufacturing Systems Laboratory for Manufacturing Planning and Control

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Abstract

Industry 4.0 is reshaping Manufacturing Planning and Control (MPC) processes in order to implement flexible and integrated manufacturing systems capable of dealing with high levels of product diversity and customisation. Smart Factories are one of the greatest products of Industry 4.0, in which all manufacturing system activities are managed and scheduled by Information Technology support systems, in real-time, according to the context where they are inserted, also referred to as Smart Manufacturing Systems (SMS). The objective of this paper is to describe the implementation of a SMS laboratory that reproduces the manufacturing environment of a Smart Factory, as well as a pilot-test of that same facility. The SMS Laboratory was designed and implemented by the academic staff from the MPC area from University of Minho (Portugal), to be used in different course units of Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) programs. The purpose is to create an active learning experience, involving hands-on activities/learning-by-doing, where students are the operators and can witness/understand how a Smart Factory should work. The SMS Laboratory consists of 7 workstations, 4 warehouses, 3 transport systems and 1 maintenance workstation, and all activities are managed by a proprietary software (SMS). During the experience, students choose the quantity and type of goods to manufacture, among 2 types of products, a dummy product with 2 variants and a flashlight with 4 variants. The operation of the facility was first tested by the authors and then a pilot-test was carried out with a group of 9 people. The test was successful and allowed to collect valuable feedback to improve the experience, to make it more dynamic and keep students' attention. Soon, the SMS Laboratory will be used by two-course units of IEM programs and the application in other areas is also being analysed, namely Production Organization, Quality Control and Maintenance Management.

Keywords: Industry 4.0; Engineering Education; Active Learning; Smart Manufacturing Systems; Smart Laboratory.

1 Introduction

Over the last centuries, the industry sector has gone through major changes to deal with technological, business, and organizational challenges. Nowadays it is globally accepted that industrial organizations are witnessing the fourth industrial revolution, also referred to as Industry 4.0. Traditional manufacturing systems relied mostly on human labour and equipment, limiting their efficiency and flexibility. The emergence of new technologies across several areas, such as automation, robotics, data analysis and information systems, marked the beginning of the fourth industrial revolution (Xu et al., 2018) – which aims to address the limitations of traditional manufacturing systems by implementing digital, smart and integrated systems (Zhou et al., 2015).

Industry 4.0 aims at a stage of full integration and synchronization between all entities of manufacturing systems, including humans, equipment, devices, and systems involved in all manufacturing processes (production, transportation, warehousing, quality control, etc.). This manufacturing environment is commonly referred to as Smart Factories, where activities are defined and supported by Information Technology (IT) support systems, in real-time, according to the context where they are inserted. IT support systems that support the management and control of manufacturing system activities are also referred to as Smart Manufacturing Systems (SMS) (Kagermann et al., 2013; Lucke et al., 2008; Zheng et al., 2018).

In Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) programs, the development of competences for Industry 4.0, Smart Factories and SMS is a matter of utmost importance, especially because Industry 4.0 is reshaping

Manufacturing Planning and Control (MPC) processes and because more and more companies need to apply these competences to become more efficient and competitive in the market.

Active learning approaches are becoming increasingly popular in engineering education because they improve student's learning ability, both in terms of technical and transversal/soft competences (Christie & Graaff, 2016; Guo et al., 2020; Lima et al., 2007; Sousa et al., 2023). The application of these approaches to the development of the competences mentioned above plays an even more crucial role because a large part of the program contents refers to a set of abstract concepts and functions that are not easily understood (since they do not exist in physical space). Therefore, when it is possible to create laboratory facilities in which students can apply these competences or witness the result of their application (involving hands-on activities/learning-by-doing), the achievement of the expected learning outcomes is more robust and faster.

This paper aims to describe (i) the implementation of a laboratory that reproduces the manufacturing environment of a Smart Factory (designated as SMS Laboratory), and (ii) a pilot-test carried out in that facility. The SMS laboratory is located in the Department of Production System (DPS) at the University of Minho, Portugal, and was designed by a group of teachers and researchers in the MPC area. The SMS Lab aims to provide an active learning experience, involving hands-on activities/learning by doing, where students from different IEM programmes play the role of operators and experience/understand how a Smart Factory works.

The paper is structured in five sections. Section 2 presents the methods used to carry out this work. Section 3 describes the implementation of the SMS Laboratory and the pilot-test of the facility. Section 4 discusses the main applications and results of the laboratory. Section 5 presents the final remarks of the paper.

2 Methods

The implementation of the SMS Laboratory was led by the authors of this paper and consisted of three stages: (i) physical implementation of the facility, (ii) informatic representation of the information needed to manage MPC processes and (iii) creation of a set of tests to validate the operation of the SMS Laboratory.

A manufacturing system consists of a set of humans, equipment and systems used throughout the manufacturing process of a product (Kosacka-Olejnik et al., 2021). To implement a manufacturing system in the facility, in the first stage, it was identified and collected some of the equipment available in the DPS, namely workstations, storage structures, material transport equipment, products to be manufactured/assembled, tables, chairs, among others. Then, the authors defined the layout of the facility and set up the SMS Laboratory. Each physical element of the manufacturing system has been labelled (visual management) to streamline the transport and storage processes. Besides that, the technological infrastructure to support the application of the software was also installed (server, terminals, network, etc.).

In the second stage all physical elements of the manufacturing system were represented in a proprietary SMS software recently developed at DPS, also referred to as "digital twin" of the manufacturing system, to "provide a mirror of physical shop floor" reflecting the "real-life" status of each object (Wang et al., 2019).

Finally, the operation of the SMS Laboratory was first tested by the authors and then a pilot-test was carried out with a group of nine people of the MPC area from the DPS (professors and researchers) to validate if the main purpose of this work were achieved: make easier to understand how a Smart Factory should work and facilitate the development of competences in this area.

3 The Smart Laboratory

This section is divided into four subsections. The first subsection shows the set of products and operations that can be executed in the SMS Laboratory. The second subsection describes the workstations and layout of the facility. The third subsection describes the information represented in the SMS software to manage all activities of the facility. The last subsection describes the tests that have been carried out so far.

3.1 Products, Items and Operations

The SMS Laboratory is prepared to manufacture six different products (Figure 1): two dummy products assembled with plastic and metallic pieces, and four flashlights with different colours. It should be noted that these are just some examples – other products can be implemented to be manufactured in the SMS laboratory.

Figure 1. Pictures of the products manufactured in the SMS Laboratory

Each product has a set of properties defining information to MPC processes, a Bill of Materials (BOM), and a routing. The BOM and routing are the list of components/parts and the sequence of operations to manufacture a product, respectively. Figure 2 depicts the BOM and routing of Dummy Product A and Red Flashlight.

Figure 2. Bill of material and routing of Dummy Product A (Black Handle – Black Base) and Red Flashlight

The manufacturing process of Dummy Product A consists of two operations: assembly and base fixing. The first requires four tubes and three units of the assembly kit (semi-finished product). The second operation can only be executed after the first and requires the black base semi-finished. Each semi-finished product needs a single operation and a set of components. The manufacturing process of the Red Flashlight starts with the assembly of the optical kit that requires the following components/raw materials: lamp holder, lamp, reflector and lamp socket. Next, the red top ring and the glass are added to the optical kit (assembly – flashlight top). The manufacturing process of the Red Flashlight ends with the joining of the flashlight top (work-in-process that results from the previous operation), the red housing, two batteries and a black O-ring. The BOM and routing of the Dummy Product B and remaining flashlight are also similar but some of the items required are different.

3.2 Manufacturing System

The manufacturing system implemented in the SMS laboratory consists of seven workstations, four warehouses/supermarkets, three milk runs (transport systems), two suppliers and a maintenance workstation. Figure 3 provides an overview of the SMS Laboratory. Table 1 contains a picture of each element.

Figure 3. Overview of the SMS Laboratory

Table 1. Workstations, warehouses/supermarkets and milk runs of the SMS Laboratory

Workstations					
	Workstation 1	Workstation 2	Workstation 3	Workstation 4	
	Workstation 5	Workstation 6	Workstation 7	Maintenance Workstation	
	Warehouses/ Supermarkets				
		Raw Materials Warehouse 1 - Metal	Raw Materials Warehouse 2 - Plastic	Semi-Finished Supermarket	Final Goods Warehouse
		Milk Runs			
Inbound Milk Run			Raw Materials Milk Run	Semi-Finished Milk Run	

Table 2 defines the set of operations each workstation can execute (referred to as workstation skills), considering the routing of each product (Figure 2). Workstations 4 and 7 execute repackaging and packaging operations (not considered in the examples presented).

Table 2. Skills of each Workstation

Workstation	Product Type	Operation
Workstation 1	Dummy Products A/B	Pre-Assembly
	Flashlights	Assembly – Optical Kit
Workstation 2	Dummy Products A/B	Pre-Assembly
	Flashlights	Assembly – Optical Kit
Workstation 3	Dummy Products A/B	Assembly
	Flashlights	Assembly – Flashlight Top
Workstation 5	Dummy Products A/B	Screwing Fixers
Workstation 6	Dummy Products A/B	Base Fixing
	Flashlights	Final Assembly

The warehouses/supermarkets are storage structures where materials should be placed and stored. The metallic raw materials are stored at 'Raw Materials Warehouse 1 – Metal'. The plastic raw materials are stored at 'Raw Materials Warehouse 2 – Plastic'. All semi-finished products are placed at 'Semi-Finished Supermarket' and all final products are placed at 'Final Goods Warehouse'.

The milk runs are responsible for transporting most of the materials over the facility, between workstations and warehouses/supermarkets. Figure 4 illustrates all milk run routes, that is, the sequence of points visited by each milk run. Each milk run route is illustrated with a different colour.

Figure 4. Scheme of milk run routes

3.3 Smart Manufacturing System

The SMS software that controls the activities executed in the SMS Laboratory is an integrated MPC system that covers four main functional areas, illustrated in Figure 5. Product Data Management refers to the functional area where all information about the products is defined and managed. The Organization Data Management is the area where all information about the entities that influence a manufacturing system is defined, including workstations, warehouses, supermarkets, transport systems, or even external entities (customers and suppliers). Production Planning and Control (PPC) (also referred to as medium-term planning) includes a set of functions that results in a plan about what must be produced, bought, or outsourced, in which quantities, in which dates and the number of resources needed to meet the plan. Lastly, the Shop-Floor Control (SFC) functional area (also called short-term planning) includes a set of functions to schedule and automatically sequence (without human intervention) all jobs and activities, to all entities that influence the manufacturing system.

Figure 5. Smart Manufacturing System – Software Architecture

The set of PPC and SFC functions implemented in the software is able to automatically manage all planning and scheduling activities in the manufacturing system (in order to implement a Smart Factory), but these functions require information of all entities and products in the manufacturing system, including information about different products, types of entities, their behaviours, properties, organization, rules and restrictions to which they are subject. Most of the information refers to the information described, in a simplified way, in the previous sections, which has been represented by the authors in the software. Some support documents (videos, images, and PDF files) of how to execute each operation were also defined in the system, to ensure that users without experience or training could execute any operation.

The SMS software interfaces to interact with final users were also defined by the authors, including those to key users (managers, planners, etc.) and work users (workers at each workstation or milk run). Figure 6 shows some examples of those interfaces. Figure 6(a) displays the number of jobs (also referred to as kanban) assigned to each workstation. Figure 6(b) shows an example of a workstation interface – in this example, the interface is suggesting starting the 'Pre-Assembly' operation of an 'Assembly Kit' at 'Workstation 1'. Figure 6(c) shows an example of a milk run interface – in this example, the interface is suggesting to the 'Semi-Finished Milk Run' to load a set of 'Assembly Kits' at position '1021' of 'Workstation 1' and place it at position '2611' of the milk run.

Figure 6. Examples of interfaces of the SMS software (a) general manager, (b) workstation, (c) milk-run

3.4 Usability and Functional Tests

The initial functional tests of the SMS Laboratory were performed by the authors to make sure the information was properly defined in the SMS software and that the facility was properly designed. Then, a pilot-test was carried out with a group of nine people of the MPC area (teachers and researchers), aiming to collect informal feedback and a critical view from people with experience and competences in the MPC area, before testing the SMS Laboratory learning experience with students. The main goal of the pilot-test was to validate if a set of products (among the products presented in Figure 1), chosen by the group at the beginning of the experience, could be manufactured in the SMS Laboratory without human interference in the planning and control of activities. The group decided to manufacture three units of red flashlights. No training was given to workers to perform the required activities. The SMS software identified and assigned all activities that needed to be executed and provided all required information for workers to execute each activity, including work instructions (videos, PDF files, etc.) or information about the positions where each object should be placed. Figure 7 shows some pictures of the pilot-test.

Figure 7. Pictures of the pilot-test

At the end of the pilot test, in a brainstorming session, workers' feedback was collected informally and recorded. Additionally, the authors made notes on their own perception of the experience.

4 Discussion

The pilot test showed that the SMS software ensured total control of the system, from the triggering of purchase orders to suppliers of components/raw materials, to dispatch to the end customer, passing through to the allocation of operations to workstations and milk runs responsible for all internal transport between warehouses/supermarkets and workstations (also managing the exact positions within each of them). From this perspective, the feedback gathered was clearly positive; the pilot test was successful as it ensured the production of the set of flashlights stipulated (without human intervention in the planning and control functions) and the group understood the importance and the comprehensiveness of the work developed. However, some problems were identified, particularly in relation to the start-up of the pilot test and the SMS software interfaces. The initial steps of the pilot test were boring for the workers who had to wait until they had raw materials/components to start working. This was because the pilot test started with the system unloaded (empty) and was further aggravated by the fact that there was only one worker assigned to the milk run. Furthermore, during the manufacturing process of the red flashlights, the authors had to provide some support at each workstation, mainly to help workers interpret the information displayed in each software interface. In fact, it was identified that in the SMS software, the workstation and milk run interfaces were giving equal emphasis to the activities to be carried out by the respective workers, as to other secondary information (e.g. workstation description). This meant that workers' perception of what they had to do (what operations and in what quantity) was not as quick as it should be.

To overcome these issues, some approaches to improve the experience (to be carried out later with the students) are being discussed and implemented, such as (i) reducing the information provided on each interface of the SMS software and emphasising the most important (to make it easier for each worker to interpret), (ii) ensuring that all workers do not have to wait at the start of the experience by increasing the number of milk runs to three and assigning additional operations to their workstations (loaded system) and (iii) defining a better strategy for introducing the learning experience (to better contextualise the students about what will happen). In the next semester, the learning experience at the SMS Laboratory will be carried out in two curricular units: Information Systems for Production, and Information Systems for Production Management, from the two IEM programs of the DPS at the University of Minho (master's in industrial management and engineering and master's in engineering and operations management, respectively). Application to other curricular units in the IEM area is also being analysed, as the SMS Laboratory can also be applied in areas such as Production Organization, Quality Control or Maintenance Management.

5 Conclusion

The technological evolutions of Industry 4.0 arise as a response to new manufacturing and planning challenges, allowing the implementation of Smart Factories. This paper describes an SMS Laboratory, developed and implemented in the DPS at University of Minho, Portugal, to reproduce the manufacturing environment of a Smart Factory, with high flexibility in terms of reconfiguration (e.g. layout, products and processes).

The pilot test carried out obtained clearly positive feedback revealing that, with some changes (already underway, to make the experience more dynamic and maintain the focus and motivation of those involved), the entire system can be, as intended, used by students, constituting an active learning experience in the broad

area of SMS. The authors acknowledge that the fact that it has only been possible to carry out a pilot test is a limitation of this study, which would require a greater volume of feedback.

By being exposed to hands-on activities and learning-by-doing principles, students will be able to witness/understand how a Smart Factory should work. The expected learning outcomes include: recognize key functional areas of MPC systems; understand the techniques and models used in MPC functional areas; implementing the techniques and models used in MPC functional areas; implement production planning and control systems in industrial environments; defining appropriate configurations for different industrial environments and with different requirements; understand the importance of information systems in the efficiency and competitiveness of organizations; apply skills acquired for the selection, evaluation and implementation of computer applications to support manufacturing planning and control systems.

The way in which the competences developed by students in this type of experience (especially in terms of technical competences) are assessed, as well as the collection of feedback on the same, is not yet completely defined, but will probably include an individual summative mini-test and a short survey, respectively. A brief workshop after the session in the laboratory is also an excellent and effective way to gather students' feedback.

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